

Accelerating the convergence of AGIS

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ABSTRACT. In a previous note (GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-071-1) the convergence of AGIS (Astrometric Global Iterative Solution) was discussed from a theoretical viewpoint and a simple extrapolation method was suggested to accelerate the convergence of the solution. In the present note, representative source and attitude data from successive iterations of a recent AGIS run are analyzed and compared with the theoretical expectations. It is shown that the proposed extrapolation actually brings very significant improvements of the source and attitude data. A practical implementation scheme is proposed. Its effectiveness in terms of the convergence is however difficult to assess except by a direct trial.

1 Introduction

Using notations from [1], the basic iteration step for solving the normal equations

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b} \tag{1}$$

can be summarized as follows:

$$\mathbf{r}^{(k)} = \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}^{(k)} \tag{2}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\delta}^{(k)} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{r}^{(k)} \tag{3}$$

$$\mathbf{x}^{(k+1)} = \mathbf{x}^{(k)} + \boldsymbol{\delta}^{(k)} \tag{4}$$

where $\mathbf{x}^{(k)}$ is the solution after k iterations, $\mathbf{r}^{(k)}$ the corresponding residual vector, $\boldsymbol{\delta}^{(k)}$ the calculated update, and $\mathbf{x}^{(k+1)}$ the solution in the next iteration. Here, \mathbf{B} is some approximation to the inverse of \mathbf{A} . The Astrometric Global Iterative Solution (AGIS) has, up until now, always been executed simply by repeating (2)–(4) until the update (essentially given by $|\boldsymbol{\delta}^{(k)}|$) was below some preset level (ϵ).

A problem with this algorithm is that the initial rapid convergence soon slows down considerably, so that a large number of iterations are needed for an acceptable result. Additionally, it turns out that although the updates are very small (e.g., on average below 1 μas for the parallaxes) after a sufficient number of iterations, the remaining actual errors are many times larger (several tens of μas). In other words, a convergence criterion based (only) on the size of the updates may not be entirely relevant.

In [1] it was shown how the convergence behaviour of AGIS could be understood in terms of the iteration model (2)–(4). After a sufficient number of iterations, the convergence rate is determined by the largest eigenvalue λ_1 of the iteration matrix $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}$. At this point, both the updates and the errors decrease by the constant factor $\lambda_1 < 1$ for each iteration, and the actual errors are $(1 - \lambda_1)^{-1}$ times larger than the updates.

The circumstance that λ_1 is only slightly less than 1 therefore accounts both for the slow convergence rate (after a number of iterations) and the observation that the actual errors are then still much larger than the updates.

In reality, we have never iterated AGIS long enough that the remaining errors are completely dominated by a single eigenvector component, corresponding to the largest eigenvalue. However, a similar (but approximate) reasoning applies to each iteration step, if we interpret λ_1 as the largest eigenvalue among the subset of eigenvectors that happen to dominate the errors at this approximation of the solution.

In order to accelerate the convergence, an algorithm was proposed in [1] which can be formalized as follows:

1. Perform a number of basic AGIS iterations according to (2)–(4), up to iteration k . In this last iteration, the update $\boldsymbol{\delta}^{(k)}$ is computed but not applied as in (4).
2. Estimate the largest (relevant) eigenvalue as the ratio of the last two updates,

$$\lambda_1 \simeq \frac{|\boldsymbol{\delta}^{(k)}|}{|\boldsymbol{\delta}^{(k-1)}|} \quad (5)$$

3. Calculate the extrapolation factor,

$$\omega = (1 - \lambda_1)^{-1} \quad (6)$$

4. Apply the extrapolated update,

$$\boldsymbol{x}^{(k+1)} = \boldsymbol{x}^{(k)} + \omega \boldsymbol{\delta}^{(k)} \quad (7)$$

5. Stop iterating if

$$\omega |\boldsymbol{\delta}^{(k)}| < \epsilon \quad (8)$$

otherwise go to Step 1.

The purpose of this note is to find out whether the above algorithm is likely to succeed. This is done by analyzing an extract of data from an actual AGIS run. Specifically, we want to:

- verify that the ratio (5) is a well-defined quantity in each iteration;
- verify that the extrapolation factor calculated in (6) is reasonable; and
- estimate how much the errors are reduced by the extrapolation step (7).

2 The data

The data analyzed here were extracted from an AGIS solution in the third test campaign of development cycle 3 (CY03-C3), called 1A_T4_29 (iterations 1 through 43) and 1D_T4_31 (iterations 45 through 48). The solution had formally converged (updates $< 1 \mu\text{as}$) after 48 iterations. 1A (or 1D?) indicates the data set used (GASS-LSS-1A, with 1 million primary sources observed over 5 years), T4 that noisy starting values were used for the source and attitude parameters, including systematic errors in the source data.

Only source, attitude and calibration parameters were estimated in this solution. Only source and attitude data were analyzed, since the calibration parameters do not seem to be a problem for the convergence.

The following data were extracted from the last five iterations (#44 to #48) and also, for comparison, from five earlier iterations (#12 to #16):

- the five astrometric parameters for a random set of 1000 primary sources spread over the whole sky
- the B-spline coefficients of the attitude quaternion for six time intervals of 120 knots (1 hour) each. The intervals are spread out over the whole mission, separated by about 305 days.

In addition, the corresponding true source and attitude parameters were provided.

The AGIS iterations may converge towards a solution that is systematically offset from the true values by a uniform rotation [2]. In order to evaluate the errors in position, proper motion and attitude, one should in principle correct the results of each iteration for this offset. For simplicity, the true source parameters and true attitude were instead rotated to agree, in a least-squares sense, with the last iteration (#48). The applied orientation correction at mid-epoch (2.5 years) was $(+22.018, -20.631, -68.011) \mu\text{as}$, and the spin correction was $(-21.860, +91.419, +11.466) \mu\text{as yr}^{-1}$.

For the source parameters, the updates and errors were computed simply as the differences $\delta^{(k)} = \mathbf{x}^{(k+1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(k)}$ and $e^{(k)} = \mathbf{x}^{(k)} - \mathbf{x}_0$, where \mathbf{x}_0 is the true (but rotated) parameter vector. Differences in α were multiplied by $\cos \delta$ to represent true angles on the sky.

For the attitude parameters, the updates and errors were similarly computed using quaternion algebra and expressed as small rotations about the instrument xyz axes. To this end, the B-spline coefficients were normalized to unit length and treated as quaternions.

3 Analysis of iterations #12, #13 and #14

3.1 Ratio of successive updates

Figure 1 shows the updates in iteration $k = 13$ for the five astrometric parameters, plotted against the corresponding updates in iteration $k - 1 = 12$. Figure 2 shows the corresponding plots for the attitude updates.

It is seen that there exists for all source and attitude parameters a very strong correlation between the successive updates of the same parameter. Regression lines, constrained to go through zero, are also shown in each diagram. The regression coefficients are computed as

$$c = \frac{\delta^{(k)} \cdot \delta^{(k-1)}}{\delta^{(k-1)} \cdot \delta^{(k-1)}} \quad (9)$$

(where δ is limited to one kind of parameter, e.g. parallax). The resulting regression coefficients, shown in Table 1, may be adopted as estimates of the largest eigenvalue λ_1 . The extrapolation factor is then $\omega = (1 - c)^{-1}$, also given in the table.

The different parameters results in estimated extrapolation factors that range from 3.82

FIGURE 1: Plot of successive updates in α^* , δ , π (top row) and μ_{α^*} , μ_{δ} (bottom row). The updates in iteration #13 are plotted against those in iteration #12. The coefficients c of the regression lines are given in Table 1.

FIGURE 2: Plot of successive updates in attitude, expressed as small rotations about the instrument x , y and z axes. The updates in iteration #13 are plotted against those in iteration #12. The coefficients c of the regression lines are given in Table 1.

to 4.92. Note that we may want to use the same extrapolation factor for all parameters, in which case we will probably choose some value in this range.

3.2 Optimum extrapolation factors

Turning now to the question whether the above extrapolation factors make sense, we note that the error of the extrapolated solution can easily be evaluated as function of ω , since we know the true parameters. The extrapolation error is

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{e}^{(k)} + \omega \boldsymbol{\delta}^{(k)} \quad (10)$$

TABLE 1: Regression coefficients c and estimated extrapolation factors $\omega = 1/(1 - c)$ for the source and attitude updates in iterations #12 and #13.

Parameter	α^*	δ	π	μ_{α^*}	μ_{δ}	x	y	z
c	0.752	0.738	0.742	0.761	0.751	0.797	0.775	0.760
ω	4.03	3.82	3.87	4.18	4.01	4.92	4.44	4.17

FIGURE 3: RMS error of the extrapolated solution in iteration #14, as function of the extrapolation factor ω . The vertical lines show the value $\omega = 3.87$ indicated by the parallax updates in the two preceding iterations (cf. Table 1).

from which

$$|e| = \left[|e^{(k)}|^2 + 2\omega e^{(k)} \cdot \delta^{(k)} + \omega^2 |\delta^{(k)}|^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

Figure 3 shows the corresponding RMS errors as functions of ω . The RMS errors are normalized to unity for $\omega = 1$, which corresponds to a normal AGIS step. It is seen that any ω in the range indicated by the analysis of the updates would provide a significant reduction (by about 40%) of the RMS error, compared to a normal AGIS iteration step.

The optimum extrapolation factors are generally a bit larger than the values estimated from the updates. However, the improvement obtained by using the optimum extrapolation factors, rather than the ones estimated from the regression coefficients, is in all cases marginal. It is also clear from these curves that if we have the choice a range of extrapolation factors, it is generally better to choose a conservative factor (which will still give some improvement) rather than a factor that may be over-estimated (which could increase the errors). It appears that the parallax updates tend to provide such a conservative estimate.

3.3 Illustration of the improvement in attitude

Further proof that the extrapolation actually works can be found by direct inspection of the attitude errors with ($\omega = 3.87$) and without ($\omega = 1$) extrapolation. Such a comparison is shown in Figure 4. It can be noted that the extrapolation in most cases seems to reduce the large excursions of the errors, i.e. it has a beneficial effect not only on the RMS errors (as shown in Fig. 3) but also on the tails of the error distribution.

FIGURE 4: The attitude errors in iteration #14 using the normal AGIS update (dashed curves) and the extrapolation (solid curves). Only two of the six attitude intervals are shown, in order to avoid graphs that are too compressed to be legible.

FIGURE 5: Plot of successive updates in α^* , δ , π (top row) and μ_{α^*} , μ_δ (bottom row). The updates in iteration #47 are plotted against those in iteration #46. The coefficients c of the regression lines are given in Table 2.

FIGURE 6: Plot of successive updates in attitude, expressed as small rotations about the instrument x , y and z axes. The updates in iteration #47 are plotted against those in iteration #46. The coefficients c of the regression lines are given in Table 2.

4 Analysis of iterations #46, #47 and #48

The analysis of the last three iterations parallels that in Sect. 3. Since the results are qualitatively similar, most of the discussion in the previous section is not repeated here.

TABLE 2: Regression coefficients c and estimated extrapolation factors $\omega = 1/(1 - c)$ for the source and attitude updates in iterations #46 and #47.

Parameter	α^*	δ	π	μ_{α^*}	μ_{δ}	x	y	z
c	0.932	0.936	0.894	0.943	0.945	0.968	0.976	0.927
ω	14.7	15.6	9.45	17.4	18.0	31.4	41.6	13.7

FIGURE 7: RMS error of the extrapolated solution in iteration #48, as function of the extrapolation factor ω . The vertical lines show the value $\omega = 9.45$ indicated by the parallax updates in the two preceding iterations (cf. Table 2).

4.1 Ratio of successive updates

Figures 5 and 6 show the updates in iteration $k = 47$ for the source and attitude parameters, plotted against the corresponding updates in iteration $k - 1 = 46$. The regression coefficients c and the corresponding extrapolation factors $\omega = 1/(1 - c)$ are given in Table 2. The extrapolation factors are not as consistent as in Table 1, and especially the factors derived from the attitude updates in x and y are much larger than the for the other parameters. The smallest (most conservative) factor is given by the parallaxes updates.

4.2 Optimum extrapolation factors

Figure 7 shows the RMS errors as functions of ω , normalized to unity for $\omega = 1$. For the astrometric parameters and the z attitude, the ω indicated by the parallax updates will give an improvement of 30–60%, while in x and y resulting errors are essentially independent of ω . Here it is very clear that the (conservative) ω from the parallaxes should be preferred.

4.3 Illustration of the improvement in attitude

Figure 8 shows the attitude errors resulting from the update with $\omega = 9.45$. As suggested by Fig. 7, the attitude in x and y (i.e., AC) is hardly affected, while the improvement in z (AL) is very significant.

FIGURE 8: The attitude errors in iteration #48 using the normal AGIS update (dashed curves or dots) and the extrapolation (solid curves). In the upper two diagrams, only two of the six attitude intervals are shown. The bottom diagram shows the attitude errors in z for all six intervals.

5 Discussion of results

In the basic AGIS iterations (i.e., without extrapolation), the ratio of successive updates appears to be approximately the same for all the updated source and attitude parameters. This is true at least in the earlier iterations (#12–14) when the solution is far from converged. In the later iterations (#46–48), some of the ratios (for the x and y components of the attitude) are however much closer to unity than the rest. This seems to be related to the circumstance that the AC attitude is then already effectively converged.

The extrapolation factors derived from the ratio of updates are reasonable, except in the cases mentioned above, namely for the last iterations of the AC attitude. The ratio of parallax updates provides the most conservative estimate, which works in all the cases. A single extrapolation can provide an improvement by 30–60% in the source and (AL) attitude parameters.

This shows that the simple acceleration algorithm outlined in Sect. 1 does in fact work. The extrapolation factor ω is best calculated from the parallax updates, using the regression method in Eq. (9), possibly modified to make it robust against outliers.

6 Implementation

As for the practical implementation of the extrapolation algorithm in AGIS, the main considerations are:

- The implementation of the extrapolation itself, Eq. (7), is a trivial modification of AGIS. However, while ω must obviously be known at the time of updating, its value is in fact determined from the updates themselves (in the same iteration). Thus we have to find a way to estimate ω before the actual updating starts.
- Clearly ω can only be estimated from a sequence of basic (i.e., non-extrapolated) AGIS iterations. Thus, the extrapolation cannot be done in every iteration, and we need to determine the sequence of basic and extrapolated iterations.
- The extrapolation can be applied either to the source updates or to the attitude updates (but not to both). Thus we have to choose one of the two possibilities.

The following two scenarios might be considered. For simplicity, only the source (S), attitude (A) and calibration (C) updates are included.

A. Extrapolation applied to the attitude: In this case the sequence could be schematically described as

$$\text{SAC } n(\text{SAC}) \text{ S} \rightarrow \omega \mathbf{AC} \ n(\text{SAC}) \text{ S} \rightarrow \omega \mathbf{AC} \ \dots \quad (12)$$

$n(\text{X})$ means that the sequence X is repeated n times. $\rightarrow \omega$ means that ω is estimated from the parallax updates in the two preceding S processes. The process using extrapolated updates is shown in boldface.

The initial SAC sequence is needed to eliminate the large initial errors in source parameters that basically have nothing to do with the attitude and calibration errors at that point. The minimum possible value for n is 1.

B. Extrapolation applied to the sources: In this case the sequence would be

$$\text{SAC } n(\text{SAC}) \text{ [S]} \rightarrow \omega \text{SAC } n(\text{SAC}) \text{ [S]} \rightarrow \omega \text{SAC } \dots \quad (13)$$

Here [S] means that updates are only computed for a small subset of the sources, but not applied – they are only used to estimate ω . The actual updating of these sources is done in the subsequent **S** process (using extrapolation). Again, the minimum possible value for n is 1.

It is not known which of these methods is the better one, which is the optimal value of n , and how much can be gained in terms of the number of iterations required for convergence. It should be noted that the new convergence criterion (8) is much stricter than the old, which may (partly?) offset the gain in convergence rate when it comes to the total number of iterations needed.

Considering the different convergence rates for the AL and AC attitude, and also that the attitude may sometimes behave erratically in certain time intervals, it appears safer to do the extrapolation in source parameters (method B). This is therefore proposed as the baseline for some first experiments, using $n = 1$.

In any case some implementation of (9) is also needed. As already mentioned, it should be robust against outliers, which suggests either an iterative procedure or the use of L_1 norm (minimising the sum of absolute deviations). It should probably also take into account the heteroscedasticity of the data. This is most easily done by using the updates normalised by their formal errors, rather than the updates themselves. Finally, a sanity check should be made, so that ω is not less than 1, nor unreasonably large ($> 20?$). The computed and used values should be logged.

References

- [1] Lindegren L., 2007: *Convergence properties of AGIS*, GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-071-1
- [2] Lindegren L., 2007: *Mathematical framework for the AGIS System Orientation*, GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-072-01

Acronyms

The following table has been generated from the on-line Gaia acronym list:

Acronym	Description
AC	ACross scan (direction)
AGIS	Astrometric Global Iterative Solution
AL	ALong scan (direction)
RMS	Root Mean Square